

ACCURACY OF CT-GUIDED CORE NEEDLE BIOPSY IN DAIGNOSIS OF THE THORACIC LESION SUSPECIOUS FOR PRIMITIVE MALIGNANCY OF THE LUNGS

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Abstract

Background: Lung cancer is a leading cause of cancer-related deaths globally and shows increasing incidence in developing countries including Pakistan. Early and accurate tissue diagnosis is essential because radiological imaging alone cannot reliably distinguish benign from malignant pulmonary lesions. CT-guided core needle biopsy (CNB) provides a minimally invasive option for acquiring adequate tissue samples for definitive diagnosis.

Objective: To determine the diagnostic accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and safety of CT-guided core needle biopsy in patients with thoracic lesions suspicious for primary lung malignancy.

Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at the radiology department of Bajwa Hospital Lahore, over four months. A total of 73 patients aged ≥ 18 years with thoracic lesions ≥ 10 mm suspicious for malignancy were included through convenience sampling. CT-guided CNB was performed using a 64-slice CT scanner and an 18-gauge coaxial automated biopsy needle. Histopathology served as the reference standard.

Results: Of 73 patients, 61.6% were male and 67.1% had a smoking history. Cough (80.8%), weight loss (76.7%), and dyspnea (68.5%) were the most common symptoms. Adequate tissue samples were obtained in 90.4% of cases and a definitive histopathological diagnosis was reached in 91.8%. Concordance between CNB diagnosis and final outcome was 93.2%. Malignancy was diagnosed in 82.2% of patients, with adenocarcinoma being the most common type (74%). Complications were minimal pneumothorax (13.7%) and mild hemorrhage (6.8%). No major adverse events were observed.

Conclusion: CT-guided core needle biopsy is a highly accurate, safe, and reliable method for diagnosing thoracic lesions suspicious for lung cancer. Its high diagnostic yield and low complication rate support its routine use in clinical practice within Pakistan.

INTRODUCTION

Lung cancer remains one of the most significant causes of cancer-related mortality worldwide, with a rising incidence in developing countries such as Pakistan. Factors such as smoking, air pollution, and occupational exposures contribute substantially to the growing burden of disease.(1) While imaging modalities such as CT and PET-CT are essential for lesion detection, definitive diagnosis requires tissue sampling because radiological findings alone may mimic infections, granulomatous disease, or benign nodules.(2) Core needle biopsy (CNB) has emerged as a preferred diagnostic tool because it provides larger, intact tissue samples suitable for histopathological and immunohistochemical evaluation.(3) Compared to fine-needle aspiration (FNA), CNB offers superior diagnostic accuracy, particularly in differentiating benign from malignant lesions and identifying specific tumor subtypes.

CT guidance enhances the precision of CNB by enabling real-time visualization of needle trajectory, allowing safe access to both peripheral and deep-seated thoracic lesions. Multiple international studies report sensitivity ranging from 87% to 96% and accuracy exceeding 90%. However, there is limited local evidence from Pakistan, where population characteristics, environmental exposures, and clinical practices differ from Western settings.(4,5) This study aimed to assess the diagnostic performance and safety of CT-guided CNB for thoracic lesions suspicious for primary lung cancer in Pakistani patients, addressing the existing research gap and contributing region-specific data.(6)

METHODS

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in the Radiology Department of Bajwa Hospital Lahore. The study duration was four months and commenced after obtaining institutional ethical approval. Patients aged 18 years and above with thoracic lesions detected on CT scan and considered suspicious for primary lung malignancy were eligible for inclusion. A total of 73 patients meeting the criteria were selected through non-probability convenience sampling. Patients with uncorrectable coagulopathy, severe respiratory compromise, highly vascular lesions, or a single functioning lung were excluded to minimize procedural risk.(7) Detailed

clinical history, including smoking status, occupational exposure, and presenting symptoms, was recorded for each participant.(8)

All biopsy procedures were performed using a 64-slice CT scanner. After explaining the procedure and obtaining written informed consent, patients were positioned depending on lesion location; supine, prone, or lateral decubitus.(9) The skin was cleansed and draped under strict aseptic precautions, and local anesthesia was administered. An 18-gauge automated coaxial core needle biopsy system was used for tissue sampling. Under CT guidance, the needle was advanced carefully toward the target lesion, with adjustments made according to real-time imaging. (10) Typically, two to three core samples were obtained from each lesion to ensure adequate tissue for histopathological assessment. Post-procedural CT scans were performed immediately to detect complications such as pneumothorax or hemorrhage, and patients were monitored in the recovery area for clinical stability. (11, 12)

All biopsy specimens were sent for histopathological examination, which served as the diagnostic reference standard. Data regarding demographics, clinical presentation, radiological characteristics, biopsy technique, and complications were documented on a structured proforma. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 25(13). Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages, whereas continuous variables were summarized as mean \pm standard deviation. Diagnostic performance, including adequacy rate, diagnostic yield, and overall accuracy, was calculated by comparing CT-guided biopsy results with final histopathology to determine the reliability of the procedure in diagnosing thoracic lesions suspicious for primary lung malignancy.(14)

RESULTS

A total of 73 patients were included in this study, of whom 45 (61.6%) were males and 28 (38.4%) were females, indicating a male predominance among patients undergoing CT-guided core needle biopsy for suspected thoracic malignancies. Regarding smoking history, 37.0% of patients were active smokers, 30.1% were previous smokers, and 32.9% had never smoked, showing that approximately two-

thirds of the patients had prior or current exposure to tobacco. Occupational exposure was noted in 42 patients (57.5%), with 30.1% exposed to dust, 19.2% to chemicals, and 8.2% to asbestos, while 42.5% had no occupational exposure of concern. The most common presenting symptom was cough, reported in 59 patients (80.8%), and followed by weight loss in 56 patients (76.7%) and dyspnea in 50 patients (68.5%). Other symptoms included chest pain (35.6%), fever (30.1%), and hemoptysis (19.2%). Comorbid conditions were present in a substantial proportion of the cohort, with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) in 17 patients (23.3%), hypertension in 16 patients (21.9%), and diabetes mellitus in 13 patients (17.8%), while 27 patients (37.0%) had no associated comorbidity, highlighting a notable burden of underlying disease in this population.

Radiologically, lesions were more frequently observed in the right lung (26 patients, 35.6%) compared to the left lung (15 patients, 20.5%), with 19 lesions (26.0%) located peripherally and 13 (17.8%) centrally. Most lesions were peripheral and isolated (79.5%), while 20.5% showed pleural attachment. Regarding lesion margins, the majority were irregular or spiculated (82.2%), with lobulated (9.6%) and smooth (8.2%) types observed less frequently. Most lesions were non-calcified and non-cavitary (71.2%), while 13.7% were calcified and

15.1% cavitary, reflecting the diverse radiologic appearances of thoracic masses.

CT-guided core needle biopsy provided sufficient tissue for histopathologic analysis in 66 patients (90.4%), and a definitive histopathologic diagnosis was achieved in 67 patients (91.8%). Biopsy results correlated with the final diagnosis in 68 patients (93.2%), indicating a high diagnostic accuracy for this procedure. Post-biopsy chest radiographs were performed in 67 patients (91.8%) to evaluate for potential complications. The procedure was generally safe, with the majority of patients (78.1%) experiencing no complications. Mild complications occurred in a few cases, including pneumothorax in 10 patients (13.7%), hemorrhage in 5 patients (6.8%), and other minor complications in 1 patient (1.4%), with no procedure-related mortality reported. Histopathologic evaluation revealed that 60 patients (82.2%) had malignant lesions, with adenocarcinoma being the most common subtype (54 patients, 74%), followed by squamous cell carcinoma (12 patients, 16.4%). Less common malignancies included neuroendocrine tumors, unclassified non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), and mesenchymal tumors, each accounting for 2.7% of cases. Thirteen patients (17.8%) had benign lesions, and only one case (1.4%) remained uncertain after evaluation. These findings underscore the high diagnostic yield and accuracy of CT-guided core needle biopsy for evaluating thoracic lesions suspected of malignancy.

Table 1: Patient demographics and clinical Characteristics with Radiologically confirmed Thoracic Lesions

Variable	value
Total Patients	73
Gender	Male 61.6%, Female 38.4%
Smoking status	Current 37%,Former 30.1%,Non-smoker 32.9%
Occupational exposure	Dust 30.1%,Chemicals19.2%,Asbestos 8.2%
Clinical Symptoms	Cough 80.8%,Weight Loss76.7%, Dyspnea 68.5%, Chest pain 35.6%, Hemoptysis 19.2%
Lesion location	Peripheral 79.5%,central 20.5%
Lesion Margin	Irregular/Spiculated 82.2%

Side Involved	Right Lung 35.6 %(Left Lung Remaining %)
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Table 2: Histopathological Diagnosis of Thoracic Lesions with Diagnostic performance of CT-Guided Core needle biopsy

Diagnosis	Percentage%
Malignant	82.2%
Adenocarcinoma	74% of Malignant
Squamous cell carcinoma	16.4% of Malignant
Benign	17.8%
Parameter	value
Adequate tissue obtained	90.4%
Definitive diagnosis achieved	91.8%
Concordance with Final Outcome	93.2%

Frequency Table

Table 1 Gender

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Male	45	61.6
	Female	28	38.4
	Total	73	100.0

A total of 73 patients were included in the study. Among them, 45 (61.6%) were males, and 28 (38.4%) were females. This indicates that male patients constituted the majority of the study Population

Table 2: Distribution of Clinical Symptoms among study Participants

Symptoms	Percentage
Cough	80.8%
Weight Loss	76.7%
Dyspnea	68.5%
Chest Pain	35.6%
Fever	30.1%
Hemoptysis	19.2%

Fig 3

Table 3: Post Procedure Complication

	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
V None	57	78.1	78.1	78.1

Valid	Pneumothorax	10	13.7	13.7	91.8
	Hemorrhage	5	6.8	6.8	98.6
	Others	1	1.4	1.4	100.0
	Total	73	100.0	100.0	

Among the 73 patients who underwent CT-guided core needle biopsy, 57 patients (78.1%) experienced no post-procedure complications, while 10 patients (13.7%) developed pneumothorax, 5 patients (6.8%) had hemorrhage, and 1 patient (1.4%) experienced other minor complications.

Fig 4
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Table 4: Histopathology Distribution

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Adenocarcinoma	54	74.0
	Squamous cell carcinoma	12	16.4
	Neuroendocrine tumor	2	2.7
	Non-subtyped NSCLC	2	2.7
	Mesenchymal neoplasm	2	2.7
	Uncertain/inconclusive	1	1.4
	Total	73	100.0

Histopathological analysis of the 73 biopsy samples revealed that adenocarcinoma was the most common histological subtype, identified in 54 cases (74.0%). Squamous cell carcinoma was reported in 12 cases (16.4%), followed by neuroendocrine tumors in 2 cases (2.7%), non-subtyped non-small cell lung carcinoma (NSCLC) in 2 cases (2.7%), and mesenchymal neoplasms in 2 cases (2.7%).

Discussion

This study evaluated the efficacy, accuracy, and safety of CT-guided core needle biopsy (CNB) in 73 patients with thoracic masses suspected of

malignancy.(15) A predominance of male patients (61.6%) and smokers (67.1%) was observed, consistent with global trends highlighting higher lung cancer prevalence among males and the well-

established link between smoking and lung malignancy. Additionally, a significant number of patients had occupational exposure to dust, chemicals, or asbestos, indicating multiple risk factors contributing to disease development. (16,17)

Clinically, the most common symptoms were cough (80.8%), dyspnea (68.5%), and weight loss (76.7%), aligning with previously reported symptom patterns for thoracic malignancies. Radiologically, lesions predominantly involved the right lung (35.6%) and were mostly peripheral and isolated (79.5%) with irregular or spiculated margins (82.2%), characteristic of malignant tumors. Most lesions were non-calcified and non-cavitary (71.2%), supporting their malignant nature. (18)

CT-guided CNB yielded adequate tissue for diagnosis in 90.4% of cases, with confirmed histopathological diagnoses in 91.8% and an agreement rate of 93.2% with final pathology, demonstrating high diagnostic accuracy (19). Adenocarcinoma was the most common malignancy (74%), followed by squamous cell carcinoma (16.4%), reflecting current trends in lung cancer epidemiology, particularly the rise of peripheral adenocarcinomas.

The procedure was generally safe, with 78.1% of patients experiencing no complications. The most frequent complications were pneumothorax (13.7%) and hemorrhage (6.8%), all managed conservatively. These results are comparable to international studies, supporting CT-guided CNB as a reliable and low-morbidity procedure for thoracic lesion assessment. (20)

Overall, these findings reinforce the role of CT-guided CNB as a highly accurate, safe, and efficient diagnostic tool, providing sufficient tissue for detailed histological and immunohistochemical analyses. (21,22) Its adoption can significantly enhance early diagnosis of thoracic malignancies, particularly in settings where minimally invasive yet precise diagnostic techniques are essential.

Conclusion

CT-guided core needle biopsy is a safe, accurate, and efficient method for diagnosing thoracic lesions with a high suspicion of primary lung malignancy. In this study, adequate tissue was obtained in 90.4% of cases, with histopathological diagnosis achieved in

91.8% and 93.2% agreement with final pathology. Malignant lesions constituted 82.2%, predominantly adenocarcinoma (74%). Complications were minimal, with pneumothorax in 13.7% and hemorrhage in 6.8%, all managed conservatively. These findings align with global evidence, supporting CT-guided CNB as a preferred, minimally invasive diagnostic approach for lung malignancy.

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